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PERCEIVE

**Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Colored collections
through AI and Virtual Experiences**

D3.2 Material Appearance Models

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Executive Summary

This deliverable reports the physically based, data-driven and hybrid approaches for the digital colour simulations of the case studies spotlighted in PERCEIVE.

Physically based models analyse the interactions between gloss, texture, translucency and colour in a metrological way, to develop an integrative model for visual appearance. Such approaches enable the characterization, communication, prediction, and rendering of the visual appearance of complex CH assets under uneven lighting conditions. To that extent, a set of visual appearance measurements is necessary. Starting with the Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function (BRDF), the spatially-varying Bidirectional Surface Scattering Reflectance Distribution Function (SVBSSRDF) and Bidirectional Texture Functions (BTF), correlation with gloss, texture, translucency and colour features are found and modelled. In PERCEIVE, such complex appearance models are specifically necessary for the polychromy and textiles scenarios, where the objects have a pronounced three-dimensionality, and attributes such as gloss and translucency. Other objects, which are rather flat and matte, such as paintings and historical photographs, can be modelled with only some of the appearance attributes such as texture and colour.

Data-driven models work around the direct explanation of the physical phenomena, by inferring appearance attributes and the changes occurring within a degradation process, from only a limited set of data, that can include partial measurements of the appearance attributes. Data-driven models use computational machine learning techniques to extract knowledge, trends, and patterns in the data that can then be generalized to a whole range of surfaces and objects.

Hybrid models combine data-driven methods with physically-based judgements. An example in this sense is a method that consists in the creation of material proxies/mock-ups of a real cultural heritage object, that are used for physico-chemical characterization of the degradation process under a controlled set of aging factors towards understanding and simulating the change in the real object that is being emulated by the mock-ups.

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1 Introduction

Sophia Sotiropoulou (FORTH)

An overarching objective of PERCEIVE is to enhance the digital capabilities of scientists and cultural institutions, thereby enabling more effective research and communication activities for the preservation and accessibility of Coloured Heritage Collections. The development of tools, services and visitor experience prototypes is designed to apply to digital representations of the objects selected as case studies. This is with a view to providing data to develop, test and showcase the PERCEIVE scenarios, as well as to assess all developed outcomes.

The objective of PERCEIVE is to propose innovative approaches to perceiving, preserving, curating, exhibiting, understanding and accessing coloured collections. Consequently, the quality of colour and material appearance of the 2D or 3D digital representations is a central focus of all efforts.

The objective of this task is to investigate colour and material appearance models that can be utilised to enhance the digital representation of coloured heritage objects, with a particular focus on the typologies considered in the PERCEIVE scenarios. In this task, new models have been developed to address the digital reconstruction of the appearance of the objects in time, both backwards and forwards. This has involved examining the challenges of reconstructing the appearance of coloured artworks in the past, back to their original state of creation as well as to predict how they might appear in the future, based on hypothetical scenarios of exposure and conservation.

Modelling the appearance of colour involves predicting how colour will appear under different viewing conditions, taking into account factors that affect colour perception, such as the illumination, the surroundings, colour vision physiology, and viewing geometry. Material models consider how the surface of a material interacts with light to produce visual properties such as glossiness, translucency, roughness, and reflectance. These physical properties influence how light behaves when it is incident on the surface of an object, which in turn affects how it is perceived by the viewer. The surface texture: smoothness or roughness, affects how light is reflected or scattered. The lustre or gloss of a surface is related to its specular reflectance. Translucent materials, such as marble, allow light to pass through surface layers and scatter from underlying layers before being

diffused. Different materials absorb and reflect light at different wavelengths, which affects their colour and appearance.

The following sections of this deliverable present different approaches to modelling colour and appearance, as developed in the various PERCEIVE tools, services or prototypes, in relation to the questions posed by PERCEIVE scenarios.

2 PERCEIVE context and state-of-the-art of models for appearance reconstruction

Sophia Sotiropoulou (FORTH), Irina Ciortan (NTNU)

All PERCEIVE scenarios must address and communicate the changing nature of colour, which directly affects the physical appearance of the object and, consequently, our perception of its aesthetic, semantic and cultural value.

The changing nature of colour, however, manifests itself in a markedly different manner in the PERCEIVE scenarios. In paintings, the alteration of colour may be attributed to a number of factors, including chemical deterioration, degradation, or the discolouration of a pigment. This may manifest as partial or extensive colour change, occurring either on the surface or in an underlying layer. Additionally, the change in colour may be the result of the ageing of the surface protective layer or the presence of surface deposits, which can extend the effect across the entire surface of the work. However, the impact of this change on the appearance of the paint surface is not uniform. In the case of the lost polychromy scenario, the questions are different. For residual ancient polychromy, the situation is furthermore complex because the pictorial layers are no longer on the surface and only small traces remain. This is mainly due to the effect of environmental or burial conditions, that entails a partial or complete loss of the paint layer, which consequently results in the loss of the colour.

2.1 Lost polychromy in ancient statues and architecture

PERCEIVE project aims to reconstruct the original appearance of ancient statues and architectural sculptures by understanding how colour was used and integrated into ancient classical art, challenging the long-standing myth of a purely "white marble" aesthetic. Through the study of paint residues, mock-ups based on existing knowledge, and ancient or historic sources, textual descriptions or iconographic representations that provide contextual examples of the use of colour, the goal is to offer a more accurate vision of ancient aesthetics and engage the public in museum settings. Technical imaging, including ultraviolet and infrared luminescence, helps detect where paint remains on statues, while digital microscopy and spectroscopic techniques like XRF and UV-VIS-NIR are used to analyse the pigments, binders, and pictorial techniques, such as preparatory layers, gilding, or burnishing. The technical images and analytical data provide essential information for the full characterisation of the material composition. However, they do not offer insight into the appearance of the coloured parts or the general impression of the sculptures in colour, as the preserved polychromy residues are too fragmentary. To cover this gap, mock-ups were created to simulate ancient painting methods, with 3D models providing digital references for all gathered data. All this data are used as input for developing appearance models that allow to explore the original texture and visual appearance of these sculptures.

2.2 Colour change in paintings and works on paper

In Scenario 2, PERCEIVE focuses on both restoring the original colours and predicting the future colour changes in three significant artworks: *The Scream* (ca. 1910) and *The Scream* watercolour lithography (1893) by Edvard Munch, and *Road in Provence* (ca. 1895) by Paul Cézanne. This process involves data from the current paintings, including HSI imaging, microfading tests, 2D scan of the painting (only for the Scream 1910?) and elemental mapping (MA-XRF), as well as data from material mock-ups and historical photographic records. To determine the pigment palette, binders, and pigment distribution, analytical and optical spectroscopic techniques such as UV-VIS-NIR reflectance spectroscopy, XRD, and MA-XRF mapping are used to reveal chemical composition and material degradation. Pigment aging was studied through mock-up aging experiments and microfading tests directly on the paintings, tracking light and humidity-induced changes. Moreover, photographic documentation, both black-and-white and colour, provided historical insights into the paintings' original appearance, aiding in digital restoration. The diverse type of data lead to the design and implementation of various data-driven appearance simulation models.

2.3 Colour change in textiles (textile and dress collections)

The PERCEIVE textile scenario addresses the challenge of preserving and reconstructing the original aesthetic of textile collections coloured with natural and synthetic dyes, which are highly prone to fading and degradation. In museums, the public often views these textiles in their faded, dulled state, losing appreciation for their historical value. For this reason, with our methodology, we propose visualizations of how the textiles might have looked originally. On the other hand, by simulating further degradation through scientific investigation, the goal is to enhance museum monitoring strategies to ensure long-term conservation and colour preservation.

Case studies include a silk kimono with faded green areas, a calico printed dress with a faded blue background, and embroidered items with tarnished metal threads. To assist in reconstructing and predicting future changes, non-invasive spectroscopic, colorimetric, and imaging data are gathered from both the original textiles and artificially aged mock-ups. Degradation is tracked through controlled aging of mock-ups, which informs the changes of the colourants in the original objects, offering insights into both historical dyeing processes and preservation strategies.

2.4 Colour change and reproduction in historical photo / film collections

Two different elements were selected for this scenario:

- Autochromes
- Lenticular Kodacolor film

2.4.1 Autochromes

PERCEIVE focuses on digitally restoring the original colours of autochromes, a pioneering colour photography process, to address issues of damage and fading. This work not only aims to recover the visual integrity of the autochromes but also to engage audiences with their unique materiality. PERCEIVE uses a custom-made high-magnification multispectral imaging system to analyse and separate the silver and dye layers, enabling more precise digital restoration of the red, blue, and green dyes, which fade at different rates. The project also aims to develop better digitization

practices by addressing misconceptions related to autochrome digitization, and it will produce a physical demonstrator that allows users to explore how the layers of an autochrome affect colour perception.

2.4.2 Lenticular Kodacolor

PERCEIVE addresses the significant challenges posed by the technological obsolescence of lenticular Kodacolor film, a once-innovative format that is now nearly impossible to reproduce using traditional methods. This early colour film, with its colour information encoded in the silver emulsion, presents unique difficulties for restoration. Reconstructing its colours digitally involves solving a complex segmentation issue—one that PERCEIVE approaches through advanced deep-learning techniques.

3 Reconstructing lost polychromy in ancient statues

Yoko Arteaga (NTNU) Donata Magrini (CNR), Roberta Iannaccone (CNR)

The persistent myth of a monochromatic aesthetic in classical antiquity has been systematically challenged by modern research.

The study of lost polychromy extends beyond mere aesthetic interest, representing a critical scientific field that focuses on the study of primary and secondary sources, drawing on and combining approaches and methodologies from different disciplines with the common goal of understanding and scientifically re-tracking the effects of material deterioration in order to recover the original visual language of ancient art.

This research combines advanced scientific analysis with rigorous archaeological investigation. Beyond simply identifying pigment residues, this interdisciplinary approach enables a deeper understanding of how colours were applied to statues and architecture. This is essential for comprehending and subsequently communicating meaning, status, and emotion. Ultimately, this research reveals a more complex and dynamic representation of ancient civilizations than was previously thought possible.

The digital reconstruction of lost polychromy on ancient artefacts represents a significant subfield of virtual archaeology and cultural heritage preservation. Early attempts at digitally reconstructing lost polychromy on ancient artefacts were often criticised for lacking authenticity and appearing unrealistic. These models frequently relied on colours that were spread out evenly, resulting in a flat approach that failed to capture the subtle visual appearance properties of real-world materials like gloss and roughness.

Our current approach aims to overcome the limitations of standard reconstruction methods by focusing on achieving more authentic colour representations.

3.1 Material appearance of lost polychromy

3.1.1 Original colours

As part of the PERCEIVE project, a selection of statues from the National Archaeological Museum of Naples (MANN) were chosen for a case study. The museum's extensive collection provided a

Figure 1: Reconstruction workflow based on five steps: identification of polychromy traces, fabrication of mock-ups and SVBRDF modelling, 3D model photogrammetry and Atlas-based segmentation.

significant number of examples, creating a rich iconographic context for comparison with related frescoes and mosaics. This comparative analysis, supported by scientific research and historical documentation, formed the basis for reconstructing the original conception of these artefacts in colour (with polychromy).

Two analytical campaigns were conducted at the MANN on selected statues, following a standardized protocol detailed in previous works [28, 27].

3.2 Reconstruction approach

The workflow for digitally reconstructing lost polychromy on classical sculptures adopted by PERCEIVE combines an experimental and computational approach based on five steps (Fig. 1):

1. Identification of polychromy traces
2. Experimental fabrication of mock-ups
3. Capturing measurements and digital modelling of mock-ups
4. Atlas-based segmentation of a sculpture modelled digitally
5. Application of mock-up models as shaders

Figure 2: Fabrication process of the mock-ups.

3.2.1 Fabrication of mock-ups

Although highly fragmented, some residual polychromy remains visible on the statues of the selected iconography, i.e. Venus, with particular interest in the Anadyomene type. The results indicate a wide colour palette used for the hair and drapery. To replicate appearance, a series of mock-ups were created using the identified materials, guided by ancient historical sources like Pliny the Elder (*Naturalis Historia*), Vitruvius (*De Architectura*), and Theophrastus (*De Lapidibus*) who provided essential descriptions of ancient painting techniques and pigment recipes [35, 52, 47].

The discovered colour palette consisted of a few key pigments, used either individually or in binary and ternary mixtures. Iron-based yellow and red ochres were identified as the primary pigments for the hair. Egyptian blue was used to create blue shades, sometimes mixed with another pigment or applied as a preparatory layer with a white pigment. In the case of the Anadyomene Venus from the Iseum of Pompeii (inv.6298), the research allowed to discover on her the drapery Egyptian blue combined with a madder lake, likely to achieve a pinkish hue. Green earth was also identified on the Lovatelli Venus (inv. 109608).

To recreate the appearance of original polychromy, two replicas of the same set of paint mock-ups were fabricated on Pentelic and Paros marble (Fig.2). Selecting a substrate similar to that in the original case study aimed to reproduce the texture, translucency, and overall impact of the marble on the final colour. The replicas were designed to simulate the complex interplay of light between the marble surface and the overlying paint layers, as well as the effect of the natural veins in the marble. To this end, a variety of pigment combinations and stratigraphies were created, adhering as closely as possible to the descriptions found in ancient sources.

The paints were applied to 36 marble cubes, each measuring 5 x 5 x 3 cm. The surface of each cube was lightly sanded to create an optimal texture for pigment application. Each surface was then divided into nine distinct squares, each measuring approximately 1.25 x 1.25 cm. This allowed different combinations of pigments to be applied to separate and limited areas (Fig. 3).

The painting layers were applied using either a ready-to-use Punic wax (from Kremer) or egg white as binding media. The selected pigment was mixed with egg white to create a priming layer.

The pigments chosen for the replicas represent the colours commonly used in the polychromy of classical Roman sculptures. These colours include red ochre, yellow ochre, green earth, Egyptian

Figure 3: Example of some mock-ups. The dimensions of the marble cube are 5 x 5 cm, and each patch has a dimension of approx. 1.25 x 1.25 cm.

blue, madder lake, cinnabar, lead white, and calcium carbonate. Lead white was used exclusively for the preparatory layer, while calcium carbonate was also added to various paint mixtures.

The marble cubes were painted following a structured approach simulating different application methods:

- **Ground Layer Options:** Four different preparatory layers were used to create the replicas: (a) no ground layer; (b) a calcite (calcium carbonate) ground layer; (c) a lead white ground layer and (d) a mixture containing a small amount of highly dispersed Egyptian blue in calcite.
- **Layering:** Pure pigments were dispersed in Punic wax and applied in single, double, or triple superimposed layers on the ground layer options.
- **Lightness variations:** In addition to pure pigments, mixtures of pure pigments with varying ratios of calcium carbonate were also applied.
- **Pigment Combinations:** Various pigment combinations of pigments were also tested, including madder lake mixed with calcium carbonate, green earth mixed with Egyptian blue, and red ochre layered over yellow ochre.

3.2.2 Material appearance modelling

To capture the appearance of the mock-ups' materials, we measure and model the spatially varying bidirectional reflectance distribution function (SVBRDF). The mock-ups were measured using an X-Rite MA-T12 multi-angle spectrophotometer. The MA-T12 instrument measures at six illumination sources and two pick-up points. Surface reflectance is measured in the range of 400 - 700nm at 10nm intervals. The illumination source is a polychromatic white LED with enhancement in the blue region of the spectrum, and its spot size is 9 mm by 12 mm. The MA-T12 also measures six texture images at an angle of incidence of 15 degrees (Fig. 4).

The twelve spectra together and the six texture images, are used in the X-Rite Pantora software [55] to obtain the material appearance models. Pantora performs a non-linear fitting to model the SVBRDF to the data and obtains the model parameters in the form of material maps. These are a three-channel diffuse colour map, a normal map, and a specular colour map, and a greyscale roughness map. Pantora also generates a Material Exchange Format (AxF) file [33] which can be used to render the appearance of the material (Fig. 5).

Figure 4: Schematic of the MA-T12 illumination and acquisition angles. Taken from [1]

Figure 5: Pipeline for SVBRDF modelling. The multi-angle reflectance and texture images of each mock-up are measured to obtain the SVBRDF in the form of an AxF file and a set of material maps.

The SVBRDF provides a comprehensive representation of how a material reflects light, accounting for both spatial and angular variations in reflectance. This level of detail is crucial for accurately reproducing the visual properties of real-world materials, particularly those with complex surface features such as gloss, texture, and roughness. By capturing both spectral and spatial information, the MA-T12 enables the creation of digital material models that closely match the appearance of the physical samples under a wide range of lighting conditions.

Once the data is processed in Pantora, the resulting material maps provide a versatile digital representation of the surface. The diffuse colour map encodes the material’s base colour, while the normal map captures fine-scale surface geometry that affects how light interacts with the surface.

The specular colour map and roughness map together define the glossiness and specular highlight behaviour, enabling realistic rendering in virtual environments. The AxF file format is a proprietary format and is compatible with a range of rendering engines and design software, facilitating the integration of these material models into digital workflows.

The measurement data, as well as material maps and AxF files, have been uploaded on Zenodo as part of a publicly available Polychromy Appearance database with over 200 mock-up materials. This database has been implemented on Streamlit [45] and it allows the user to search for the mock-up they are interested in, in an interactive way. With drop-down menus, the user can narrow their search by querying different categories such as type of marble, type of binder, pigment, ground layer and number of paint layers. The user can view and download this data to generate their own shaders based on the material maps or directly use the AxF file for their desired application.

3.3 Polychromy SVBRDF

3.4 Atlas-based segmentation and semantic shading

The segmentation (see Figure 6) and semantic shading of the different segments of the 3D model involves the following steps:

- 3D digitization of the statue using photogrammetry or other AI/non-AI approaches. In this case study, we utilized photogrammetry to digitize the Anadyomene Venus.
- Then, inspired by path planning approaches used in robotic applications, we render the minimum number of multi-view images required to cover the entire 3D surface. The entire implementation was done in Blender.
- We select a few images from the rendered multi-view images, which are then segmented using Segment Anything. The segmentation masks generated by the AI are then refined using user guidance before being tracked to all the segments using an AI-based zero-shot tracker.
- The segmented multi-view images are then projected back to generate a 2D parametrised segmentation map over the 3D surface. We name this process ‘segmentation atlas’.

This 2D representation of the 3D surface (segmentation atlas) is used to apply the different materials captured by the spectrophotometer as previously explained. We use a modified Cook-Torrance shading model to apply the different material-maps generated by the material capture process. This allows us to apply different materials to the different segments and perform various simulations of the restoration process with each segment. Figure 7 shows a particular example using our approach:

Figure 6: Pipeline for generation 2D parametrised segmentation map from the 3D model

Figure 7: Segmentation and Reconstruction Hypothesis. On the left the segmentation of the statue using non-representative colours to define distinct segments. On the right one possible reconstruction hypothesis, utilizing material modelled from the paint mock-ups, applied to the segments.

4 Modelling colour change in paintings and works on paper

Irina Ciortan (NTNU), Panos Siozos (FORTH), Letizia Monico (CNR), Irina Sandu (MUNCH)

This section focuses on methods and workflows developed in the Perceive project based on the case studies provided for Scenario 2: Colour changes in Paintings and Works on paper. Simulation of light-induced colour change had to be applied on pigment mock-ups first, via accelerated aging. Then, one of the approaches used for predicting discoloration in paintings, models changes of the mockups, in the colour domain as linear functions, and then transfer them to a real painting. The other approach models the changes in the spectral domain, using hyperspectral images of the painting as input, where spectral unmixing is used to correlate the mockups with the pigments distribution in the real painting. Beside mockups, both methods have been successfully tested on *The Scream (ca. 1910)* by Edward Munch.

Another complementary computational method is presented for studying the temporal evolution of *The Scream (ca. 1910)* and its changing appearance due to the effects of light, moisture, and material ageing. This approach focuses on colour reconstruction using four historical colour photographs from 1971, 1989, 1993, and 2003. To address the challenges of film degradation, the method employs stable reference areas of the painting for advanced colour correction, enabling more faithful digital renderings of its appearance at several points in the 20th century.

4.1 Colour change simulation informed by artificially aged mock-ups

4.1.1 Photochemical colour change model for predicting pigments discolouration

4.1.2 General Description

The photochemical model presented in this section is one of the two approaches integrated into the Light Damage Estimator (LDE) tool. It offers a mechanistic framework for predicting pigment colour change by linking light absorption to the underlying chemical reactions that drive degradation. In this approach, colour shifts in the CIE L*a*b* space are correlated with the gradual reduction of pigment concentration caused by photochemical processes. The model incorporates both the spectral distribution of the light source and the kinetics of pigment degradation, allowing long-term changes to be expressed as a function of radiant exposure [43]. Unlike the statistical model, which relies on empirical fitting of observed data, the photochemical model offers a process-based interpretation that connects measurable colour alterations directly to the physicochemical mechanisms of light-induced pigment transformation.

4.1.3 Model Workflow

The colour change methodology is organized into two complementary workflows (Figure 8). The first workflow focuses on the experimental determination of model parameters using artificially aged pigment mock-ups, while the second applies these parameters to real artworks to estimate colour alterations after prolonged illumination.

Workflow 1: Experimental determination of model parameters The initial workflow involves the systematic collection of experimental data from artificially aged mock-ups prepared with

Figure 8: The two workflows of the photochemical colour change methodology.

pure pigments. Each pigment is exposed to controlled artificial ageing using several light sources, each characterized by distinct spectral features. For every light source, the CIE $L^*a^*b^*$ chromatic coordinates are measured at successive ageing intervals and plotted against the corresponding radiant exposure values. In parallel, the spectral power distribution (SPD) of each light source is recorded, and the associated light source classification values (VR, VG, VB) are calculated [43]. These datasets provide the foundation for fitting the colour change model. By applying the model to the CIE $L^*a^*b^*$ coordinates of the artificially aged mock-ups, linear regression yields the coefficients a and b of Equation (2). These coefficients quantitatively describe the colour evolution of each pigment under specific lighting conditions. Once derived, they are stored in a database and subsequently used for predictive simulations on real artworks.

Workflow 2: Application to real artworks The second workflow applies the model directly to cultural heritage objects. The process begins with the identification of specific-coloured regions in the artwork that correspond to pigments previously characterized in the laboratory. From these regions, the initial CIE $L^*a^*b^*$ chromatic coordinates are extracted. To simulate long-term colour changes, the user specifies the illumination dose that the artwork will experience. This dose is calculated based on:

- the total number of years of display,
- the average number of illuminated days per year,
- the daily exposure duration (hours per day), and

- the irradiance of the chosen lighting source.

Additionally, the user provides the light source classification values (VR, VG, VB), ensuring that the illumination is characterized consistently with the experimental conditions. By integrating these parameters with the model coefficients derived in Workflow 1, the methodology predicts the expected chromatic alterations. The outcome is expressed as new CIE L*a*b* coordinates, representing the pigment colour after the simulated ageing period.

4.1.4 Light Source Classification Based on Spectral Power Distribution

We adopt a simplified approach for classifying light sources according to their spectral characteristics. This method is designed to be accessible to users without specialist expertise. The classification scheme categorizes light sources based on the distribution of their emission across spectral ranges corresponding to the three primary colours of light as perceived by the human eye within the visible spectrum. This approach is consistent with museum lighting practices, where emissions outside the

Table 1: Spectral ranges selected for the calculation of a light source percentage of power distribution.

Classification	Low (nm)	High (nm)
Red spectral range (R)	380	500
Green spectral range (G)	500	600
Blue spectral range (B)	600	780

visible range are typically filtered out. As a result, each light source can be described using only three values, which represent the percentage of power emitted in the red, green, and blue spectral regions of the visible range (Table 1). For each light source, the values VR, VG, and VB correspond to the fraction of emission within the respective spectral range relative to the total emission across the 380–780 nm interval:

$$V_{R,G,B} = \frac{\text{Red, Green, Blue spectral range}}{\text{Total emission in visible (380–780 nm)}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

The model presumes that colour changes induced by light are determined mainly by the intensity of radiation within the spectral band to which a pigment is most responsive (VR, VG, or VB), rather than by the total irradiance across the visible spectrum. Said otherwise, when a pigment is exposed to light concentrated in its most sensitive wavelength region, the extent of colour alteration will be similar to that observed under full-spectrum illumination, provided the effective portion of irradiance remains equivalent. Based on this, photodegradation arises specifically from the segment of the spectrum that the pigment absorbs.

4.1.5 Photochemical Colour Change Model

The model implemented in the Light Damage Estimator (LDE) tool assumes that colour changes in a material, expressed as shifts in the L*, a*, and b* values (which correspond to variations in the visible diffuse reflectance spectra), are primarily driven by photochemical reactions affecting the pigment. These reactions alter the pigment’s chemical composition, leading to a reduction in its original concentration. The model therefore correlates colour change directly with the decrease in

pigment concentration. It is important to note, however, that other factors—such as loss of surface gloss or yellowing of the binding medium—may also influence colourimetric measurements. While these effects are not accounted for in the model, they should be considered when interpreting results. When exposed to light, the material absorbs radiation, triggering photochemical reactions that gradually reduce pigment concentration. At low levels of light absorption (zero-order kinetics), the rate of this reduction is proportional to the absorbed energy. As pigment concentration decreases, the fraction of incident radiation interacting with pigment molecules also changes, influencing the rate of degradation.

Assumption 1 Photochemical reactions in pigments are generally slow, producing only minor changes in pigment concentration during typical exposure times. This assumption is valid for gradual degradation processes, where pigment concentration remains nearly constant over the observation period. It also provides a useful metric for assessing the sensitivity of colour or reflectance shifts to small pigment losses. By tracking reflectance or colour values over time, even subtle degradation can be detected and quantified.

Assumption 2 Any colorimetric change C , whether expressed in the CIE Lab* colour space, as ΔE_{1976} , or as diffuse reflectance variations, is assumed to be proportional to the pigment concentration n in the paint. From this assumption, the following expression is obtained:

$$C = -\frac{1}{A} \ln\left(\frac{\varepsilon n_0}{\Phi}\right) + \frac{1}{A} \ln(E_0) = a + b \ln(E_0) \quad (2)$$

In this formulation, the quantum yield Φ represents the efficiency of the photochemical process, defined as the number of molecules degraded per photon absorbed. Although Φ could, in principle, be experimentally determined through chemical or spectroscopic analysis, in the present model it functions as a proportionality factor embedded within the slope of the linear relationship between colour change and the logarithm of radiant exposure (see Equation 2). Consequently, both Φ and the molar absorptivity ε are not measured directly but are incorporated implicitly through empirical validation, thereby supporting the model’s applicability to light-induced colour change data derived from mock-up experiments. As currently formulated, the model is optimized for single pigments or simple binary mixtures in which one pigment exerts dominant control over the observed colour. Extending the model to more complex systems, such as multi-pigment mixtures, would require accounting for the distinct spectral sensitivities, degradation kinetics, and potential interactions among different pigments. This includes modeling how each pigment contributes to overall reflectance and how their individual photodegradation pathways evolve—either concurrently or competitively—over time. The model also assumes a constant oil-to-pigment ratio and attributes colour changes primarily to pigment degradation. In practice, however, variations in binder-to-pigment ratios can significantly affect optical properties such as surface gloss, scattering, absorption, haze, and translucency. Under these conditions, degradation of the binder may have an equally or even more pronounced impact on colour change than pigment alteration alone.

4.1.6 Calculating the Model’s Coefficients for a Pigment

Light-induced colour change in the paint is determined not by the total irradiance over the entire emission spectrum, but by the irradiance in a specific spectral region that corresponds to the part of the spectrum that the pigment absorbs, i.e. the spectral region that is most sensitive. In this context,

Figure 9: Plots of ΔL^* , Δa^* and Δb^* values obtained with the colour-change model for Prussian blue-lead white oil paints, shown as a function of total radiant exposure (i–iii) and of the spectral radiant exposure components (iv–vi). The coefficients a and b are derived from the linear fits and subsequently stored for use in colour-change prediction.

it is not necessary to consider the total irradiance that illuminates the material. Instead, only the fraction corresponding to the spectral component that affects the pigment should be considered. To determine the spectral component affecting the pigment, we plotted the values of ΔL^* , Δa^* , and Δb^* as a function of each of the spectral components R, G, B of the radiant exposure for each light source. The three spectral components of radiant exposure were calculated using the following equations:

$$H_{B,G,R} = \frac{V_{B,G,R}}{100} H_{\text{Total}} \quad (3)$$

where H_{total} is the total radiant exposure, V_B , V_G and V_R the percentage of emission in the specific spectral range derived from Equation 1, and H_B , H_G , H_R the blue, green and red radiant exposures, respectively.

To quantify these observations, the colour-change model described in this chapter was applied to establish predictive relationships for colour evolution. Following Equation 2, the natural logarithm of both the total radiant exposure and the spectral component-specific radiant exposures was calculated. The resulting ΔL^* , Δa^* and Δb^* values obtained under different light sources were plotted against the logarithm of radiant exposure for Prussian blue–lead white paint mock-ups (Figure 9). In all cases, the colourimetric shifts exhibited a pronounced linear dependence on radiant exposure when represented on a logarithmic scale, thereby supporting the validity of the proposed model. The fitting-derived coefficients a and b for each colour coordinate are subsequently stored and employed to predict colour changes in artworks.

4.1.7 Application of the Colour-Change Model to Artworks

The calculation of colour change in artworks is based on the user-provided input of radiant exposure (light dose) together with the selection of the pigment of interest. These two parameters form the starting point for the prediction process. Using Equation 2, the model determines the expected colour shifts, expressed as ΔL^* , Δa^* and Δb^* , for the chosen pigment under the specified illumination conditions. To translate these shifts into perceptible changes, the calculated ΔL^* , Δa^* and Δb^* values are added to the current CIE Lab* coordinates that describe the pigment’s colour within the artwork. This operation results in a new set of colour coordinates that represent the predicted appearance of the pigment after exposure to the given light dose. In practice, this approach allows users to simulate the progressive alteration of colour in a specific pigment region of an artwork, thereby providing a quantitative basis for visualising and anticipating the impact of light-induced degradation over time.

4.1.8 Data-driven pigment photo-degradation model in the hyperspectral domain

In the context of pigment degradation modelling, previous knowledge on the material palette is very meaningful as it facilitates the creation of mock-ups, where swatches of fresh pigments are created to resemble the chemical composition of the artwork, and then artificially aged in a weathering chamber where environmental parameters such as light and relative humidity can be controlled. In this colour change simulation approach, we combine artificially aged mock-ups with a hyperspectral image of the artwork under investigation. More precisely, as shown in the diagram in Fig. 10, we perform spectral linear unmixing in the hyperspectral image, using least-squares minimization and assuming known spectral signatures of the pure pigments (also known as endmembers in the spectral imaging field). After unmixing, we obtain the abundance maps for each endmember. Then, we can reconstruct the painting by re-mixing the abundance maps with the artificially aged spectra of those

Figure 10: Our data-driven photodegradation models needs as input a hyperspectral image of the artwork and a set of spectral measurements of the material palette, at various aging levels.

endmembers included in the mock-ups, following the same linear mixing model. Nonetheless, the mixing techniques in paintings are commonly of non-linear nature, as there could be superimposed layers or chemical mixture between various materials. To account for the limitations of linear spectral unmixing and mixing models when it comes to paintings, we operate in the absorbance space, $-\log(R)$, where R is the reflectance. This is based on the findings of Valero et al. [49] who proved that linear unmixing in the absorbance space, $-\log(R)$, is as efficient as non-linear unmixing in the reflectance space for paintings' decomposition.

The material palette of *The Scream* (ca. 1910) is known from previous analytical studies and it includes the following pigments: vermilion, cadmium yellow, chrome yellow, viridian, cobalt blue, ultramarine blue, two types of red lake, zinc white, lead white and possibly red lead. To assess light-induced damage and predict future appearance of the artworks, in the context of PERCEIVE several such mock-ups were created by CNR and MOLAB that were later artificially aged. A subset of the palette was chosen for the *The Scream* (ca. 1910) case study according to the transience level of the pigments and so we created mockups of vermilion, chrome yellow, cadmium yellow, zinc white, lead white, and red lead. In addition, the painting was scanned with a hyperspectral imaging system under a MOLAB campaign in 2017.

Thus, to pursue the spectral unmixing task, the spectral signatures of the endmembers in *The Scream* (ca. 1910) have a diverse provenance: some are given by the mock-ups (that only partly cover the painting palette), others are extracted from the spectroscopic measurements on the painting (cardboard substrate, red lakes) and the remaining ones from a privately shared spectral library, with pigments mixed in egg-tempera medium. The reflectance spectra of the endmembers are plotted in Fig. 11. The accelerated aging experiment exposed the mockups to $33.06 W/cm^2 \cdot hr$ of total light irradiation under a UV-filter Xenon lamp. The spectral measurements were collected at 8 discrete time steps, including t_0 . To access unmeasured time steps within the monitored time-span, we interpolate in-between these discrete 8 aging steps. Specifically, an aging polynomial is fitted for each pigment using spline interpolation in the spectral domain, where the dependent variable is the total exposure (in either irradiance or illuminance units).

The spectral unmixing is carried out in the spectral range from 400 to 850 nm and yields the distribution of pigments over the entire surface of the artwork. The pigment maps (see Fig. 13) show a reasonable distribution and are comparable with the results of analytical techniques. For

Figure 11: Endmembers considered for the spectral unmixing of *The Scream*

Figure 12: The aging of vermilion monitored at discrete time steps (left) and the interpolation of intermediate steps, sampled every $0.15 \text{ W/cm}^2 \cdot \text{hr}$. As the light exposure increases, the reflectance decreases in the right tail of the spectrum, meaning that the red colour of vermilion becomes darker and less saturated.

Figure 13: The pigments maps of *The Scream*, where the red false colour indicates areas with a higher concentration of a material. The photodegradation of the pigments in the top row can be predicted, as aging data was collected for their corresponding mockups.

Figure 14: XRF maps for mercury (Hg), chromium (Cr) and cadmium (Cd) chemical elements, associated with vermilion, viridian and cadmium yellow pigments.

instance, in the case of the inorganic pigments, such as vermilion the abundance maps are compatible with the XRF maps of the associated chemical elements, mercury (Hg) and chromium (Cr), respectively, and both indicate the presence of the pigments in similar locations, as can be noticed in Fig. 14. Nonetheless, the two abundance maps that represent cadmium yellow in two chemical states (including the cubic form) do not manage to fully capture the cadmium element. This is especially obvious in the depiction of the lake area in the painting, where the yellow ellipse-shaped strokes are erroneously and partially attributed to chrome yellow instead, by the spectral unmixing model. One reason for this could be limited spectral range (visible-near infrared) that we operate in, where the yellows have less discriminative features as opposed to the ultraviolet range.

Figure 15: Current state of The Scream, as scanned in 2017 (left), and the future version, simulated for a total exposure of $34.5 \text{ W/cm}^2 \cdot \text{hr}$ under a Xenon light source (right). The darkening of vermilion is evident in the brushstrokes in the sky.

Given the abundance maps and the aging polynomial for some of the pigment, we can now simulate further damage by recombining the pigments maps with the aged spectra. The pigments whose aging behaviour we haven't measured are left unchanged, as in their current state. Figure 15 proposes a degraded version of the painting, equivalent to $34.5 \text{ W/cm}^2 \cdot \text{hr}$. In the simulation, the brushstrokes in the sky that correspond to vermilion get overall darker, which is a good result, and consistent with our other simulation methods, presented later in this chapter. One limitation of our approach is that not all the pigments in the painting have had aging data collected. Nonetheless, this is a data capture limitation, and not a method limitation, because our method can accommodate additional aging data for all the endmembers.

4.2 Modelling colour change using film archival records as temporal reference

4.2.1 Black and white film modelling

Method 1: Methodology for Assessing Colour Alteration through Historical Black and White Photography and Hyperspectral Imaging

Since its earliest days, photography has been adopted and widely used in museums as a technique that provides visual documentation and supports archival and conservation practices. From the 19th century onwards, museums have embraced photography as a precise and efficient means for documenting objects and interventions, recording exhibitions, and preserving visual evidence of artworks and cultural artefacts. These monochrome photographs are valuable historical records that can provide otherwise lost information about the condition and appearance of artworks in the past [51].

Figure 16: “The Gates of Hell” in Munch’s winter studio at Ekely. Photograph of Edvard Munch’s artworks taken in 1938. *The Scream* (1910?) is visible on the left side of the door, above two other paintings, *Anxiety* and *Despair* (Photo: R Væring, MM.D.02386 © Munchmuseet, 1938?) (left). Magnified view of “The Gates of Hell”, presenting *The Scream* (1910?) painting (right).

In this study, we investigate whether historical monochrome photographs can be systematically used to detect changes in artworks, with a particular focus on identifying colour changes [44].

The approach is applied to a case of exceptional cultural significance: Edvard Munch’s *The Scream* (1910?). This iconic painting, renowned worldwide as a symbol of modern anxiety and despair, represents a unique piece of art both artistically and historically. Understanding its material evolution over time is critical not only for its preservation but also for ensuring that future generations experience the artwork, knowing and understanding as closely as possible how it was in its original appearance.

Recent advances in spectral imaging and computational modelling now enable accurate reconstructions of historical photographic processes, offering new opportunities for non-invasive comparative study of the past and present condition of artworks through comparison of historical photographs and equivalent contemporary simulations. By combining these technologies, we aim

to explore material changes in *The Scream* and assess the broader potential of this methodology for cultural heritage studies.

Orthochromatic photograph of Munch’s paintings For the analysis, we used a copy of a digitized photograph taken on monochrome film by Edvard Munch in his studio in 1938, which captures several of his famous paintings (Figure 16). The film used was an Agfa Chromo-Isolar-Platte with an orthochromatic emulsion. Orthochromatic film is primarily sensitive to the blue and green regions of the visible spectrum, while being largely insensitive to red light. As a result, red areas in the original paintings appear black or very dark in the photograph.

The digital image of the historic photograph was cropped, resized, and geometrically registered to the sRGB image reconstructed from the multispectral data recently acquired on *The Scream* (1910?).

To make a meaningful comparison between the images, it was first necessary to compensate for the non-linear response of the film used in the 1938 photograph. Photographic films, such as the orthochromatic one used in this study, exhibit a nonlinear response characterized by the Hurter–Driffield (H–D) curve [22]. To correct for this nonlinearity, an H–D correction was applied to the scanned photograph.

Figure 17: Graph showing the Hurter–Driffield (HD) correction applied to the orthochromatic image (left). Graph showing the relative sensitivity of the orthochromatic film at the wavelengths corresponding to the multispectral channels (middle). Linear calibration curve based on pixel intensities from green-coloured areas of the corrected 1938 photograph and the simulated orthochromatic multispectral image (right).

The normalized pixel intensity E , representing film density, was mapped to the relative normalized exposure y using:

$$E = -\frac{1}{a} \ln \left(\frac{1}{y + \varepsilon} - 1 \right) + b \quad (4)$$

where ε is a small constant to avoid division by zero, with $a = 12$ and $b = 0.45$.

This correction linearizes the pixel response, enabling direct comparison with the simulated orthochromatic images. The H–D correction curve and the corrected image are presented in Figure 17 left.

Multispectral imaging of the Scream (1910?) Multispectral analysis of *The Scream* was carried out using a prototype scanner developed by CNR-INO, based on a point-scanning approach

[6]. A single photodiode per wavelength captures the radiation reflected from the surface during a vertical boustrophedon scan, producing high-quality reflectograms.

The system simultaneously acquires 32 narrow-band images (16 VIS: 390–780 nm, 16 NIR: 750–2500 nm). The scanner includes an XY(Z) scanning unit with high-precision stages and an optical head that uses a $45^\circ/0^\circ$ illumination/observation geometry with halogen lamps and high-power LEDs.

Collected radiation is focused onto a 6×6 optical fiber bundle leading to an array of Si and InGaAs photodiodes, each with narrow-band filters. Calibration uses certified colour standards and an in-scene white reference. The 16 channels in the visible range (390 to 780 nm) were used to generate the simulated orthochromatic image.

Methodology for generation of simulated orthochromatic image from multispectral data Ideally, the orthochromatic photograph would be replicated today using analog film to support the validation of the simulation. However, this is not feasible due to strict conservation protocols and the practical difficulties of reproducing historical photographic conditions, such as the original film stock, camera settings, and development processes.

As an alternative, multispectral imaging provides a flexible, accurate, and non-invasive method for simulating various black-and-white photographic responses. This makes it particularly well suited for sensitive cultural heritage objects, where direct analog reproduction is not possible.

The relative spectral sensitivity of the orthochromatic emulsion was obtained from literature data [53]. A sensitivity coefficient was assigned to each multispectral channel in the visible range (Figure 17 middle).

The simulated orthochromatic pixel intensity was calculated as:

$$I_{\text{pixel}} = \sum_i I_{\text{pixel}}(i) S(i) \quad (5)$$

where $I_{\text{pixel}}(i)$ is the pixel intensity in channel i , and $S(i)$ is the corresponding sensitivity coefficient from Figure 17 middle. Finally, pixel intensities were subsequently normalized across the full dynamic range.

Intensity calibration of the 1938 image To enable a more accurate comparison between the simulated orthochromatic image and the corrected orthochromatic image from 1938, a calibration of pixel intensities was performed.

Pixels within a green region to the right of the image were selected to construct a calibration curve. The green area was chosen because it is mainly composed of chromium-based green pigments (viridian or chromium oxide) [38], which are known for their chemical stability [40]. As a result, any colour changes over the years are expected to be insignificant.

However, it is important to consider that the complete paint system, including the binding medium, may still have experienced aging-related changes. Environmental exposure may have led to yellowing or other physical or chemical alterations in the binder, potentially affecting the appearance of the green area. Although this region was selected based on the presumed stability of its pigments and the absence of visible degradation, possible changes in the binder or surface condition could introduce uncertainties into the calibration process.

The calibration curve was generated by plotting the pixel intensities from the green area of the 1938 image against the corresponding pixel intensities from the simulated image (Figure 17 right).

A linear regression was applied, and the resulting equation was used to adjust the pixel intensities of the 1938 image accordingly.

Figure 18: A side-by-side comparison between the corrected 1938 photograph and the simulated orthochromatic image, allowing observation of differences in the dark blue areas (a) and yellow areas (b).

Evaluation of the reconstruction A methodical visual comparison of the two images was conducted. This examination revealed prominent differences in specific areas of the painting, particularly within three distinct colour ranges associated with specific pigments. These differences suggest possible colour changes in areas where these pigments are predominant (Figure 18).

The first and most striking change was observed in the blue areas (Figure 18a), where the originally dark blue shades appear to have brightened over time. While changes in blue pigments have been previously reported in other paintings by Edvard Munch, they have primarily involved a darkening phenomenon associated with ultramarine and cobalt blue [4, 5].

In contrast, the present study on *The Scream* (1910?) identifies a distinctly different alteration characterized by a brightening of the blue areas, which to our knowledge has not been documented before.

Macro X-ray fluorescence (MA-XRF) mapping of the artwork, carried out as part of a MOLAB campaign in 2017 [7], indicates that the primary pigment used in the vivid blue regions exhibiting this brightening effect is ultramarine, a complex sodium aluminosilicate containing sulfur. Cobalt blue, also known as Thenard’s blue, was also identified but appears to have been used only in specific details.

One possible explanation for the observed colour change is dissociation of the oil binder, resulting in colour desaturation and a visual appearance closer to that of the unbound pigment [14, 15]. This remains a working hypothesis.

Finally, changes in the yellow areas were observed, particularly a decrease in lightness (Figure 18b). These changes are likely related to degradation of cadmium yellow pigments, a phenomenon previously documented [50]. Investigations have shown that specific cadmium yellow formulations can fade under exposure to high relative humidity and light [32].

Figure 19: The analogue photographs of *The Scream* in 1971 (Kodak Ektachrome), 1989 (Agfa), 1993 (Agfa), and 2003 (Fuji 35 mm).

The methodology presented demonstrates that the combined use of historical black-and-white photographs and modern spectral imaging provides a powerful, non-invasive approach for detecting material and colour changes in artworks over time. By simulating the spectral sensitivity of the orthochromatic film used in a 1938 photograph of Edvard Munch's *The Scream* (1910?) and reproducing a corresponding image from recent multispectral data, significant colour changes were identified.

Specifically, a brightening of the dark blue regions and a fading of the yellow areas were observed. These findings highlight the potential of historical photographic records, when properly calibrated and compared with modern imaging data, to uncover previously ignored aspects of an artwork's material history.

This approach can be broadly applied to other cultural heritage objects, offering a robust, non-invasive, and data-driven methodology for tracking the evolution of artworks over time.

4.2.2 Colour film modelling

Based on Munch museum's archival records, *The Scream* (ca. 1910) was documented with 4 colour photographs from 1971, 1989, 1993 and 2003, shown in Fig. 19. The challenge is that some of these photographs were themselves subject to degradation, as it is obvious with the one from 1971, where the cyan dye heavily faded. In this approach, we aim to apply a colour correction so that the photographs become more reliable in revealing the past colours of the painting.

In the first step of our approach, we adjust the spectral densities of the cyan, magenta, and yellow dyes so that they match the original concentrations, taking the black level in the film as reference [8]. To this purpose, we need the spectral densities of the photograph, so we captured it with a hyperspectral transmittance imaging setup. The dye adjustment result, displayed in Fig. 20 is a more chromatic balanced film record of the painting, where the magenta colour cast is toned down and the cyan dye is slightly reinjected into the image.

In the second step, we develop a film to painting transformation, where we correct the colours

Figure 20: The hyperspectral transmittance imaging setup (left), the film record from 1971 in its original version (middle) and after pre-processing step with chromogenic dye adjustment (right) that reduces the magenta cast.

of the film record using the painting as reference. From prior chemical, analytical and accelerated aging investigations, we are aware of which materials and areas in the painting have changed. More precisely, it is known that the vermilion has darkened due to light-exposure, and that cadmium yellow has faded due to humidity. From the XRF analysis, we have the accurate distributions of these pigments in the artwork (see Fig. 14). In addition, the painting suffered a water damage in the bottom left corner. We assume the rest of the painting is stable and has not changed during the last decades. We assume that apart from these changes, the rest of the painting is stable and has not changed during the last decades. These stable areas become anchor points to define a transformation from the colours of the slides to the recent colours of the painting last captured in an imaging campaign in 2017, as portrayed in Fig. 21.

Mathematically, we formalize the film-to-painting correction with least-squares regression of polynomial models (first-order, second-order, third-order) and neural network fitting with a shallow feed-forward neural network with one hidden layer [11]. We choose the best model according to the mean absolute error given a train-test split of the data, which in our case is the shallow neural network [10]. Finally, we apply the resulting transformation to each film (see Fig. 22), which ultimately enables us to peek into the painting’s past with improved colour accuracy.

Generally, one of the challenges of digital restoration approaches resides in the lack of ground truth. A work-around the lack of ground truth is to check the consistency of well-known colour change behaviours of some pigments. We expect the vermilion to darken and cadmium yellow to fade with the passing of time, and this is perceivable in our results displayed in Fig. 23.

Moreover, this approach for digital restoration can be improved iteratively, with different change maps. In the timeline of the PERCEIVE project, the modelling of the B & W photographs was done after the processing based on the colour photographs. One conclusion of the B & W approach is that the ultramarine blue altered as well. Therefore, in a future iteration, the map of the ultramarine blue can be included as an unstable area.

Figure 21: The stable areas in the painting (not covered by white in the above images) become anchor points for establishing a film-to-paint correspondence.

Figure 22: The corrected film records (in order: 1971, 1989, 1991, 2003) following the neural network transformation based on the anchor points between the recent colours of the painting (2017) and each film.

Figure 23: In the colour corrected versions of the films from 1971 and 2003, we can notice the darkening of the vermilion brushstrokes in the sky, and the fading of the cadmium yellow especially in the lake area, on the face of the character and on the upper left side.

5 Modelling colour change in textiles (dress and tapestry collections)

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Heritage textiles are known for containing dyes particularly sensitive to photodegradation. For this reason, their virtual restoration and prediction of further discoloration are of especially high importance towards their documentation and preservation. Digital computation techniques introduce innovative approaches to realistically depict aging processes without intervention on the real objects. In this sub-chapter, we present an approach for modelling and visualizing colour changes in two textiles housed by the Victoria and Albert museum: a 20th-century silk kimono and a 19th-century printed cotton Victorian dress, dyed with natural and synthetic materials, respectively. Our simulations are rendered in the three-dimensional space, providing a realistic and interactive environment for scrutinising the different hypotheses regarding the past and future appearance of the textiles.

Our model combines an *atlas-based material segmentation* with advanced colour restoration techniques to transfer the material appearance from textile mock-ups to the 3D models of the garments [41]. Fading effects are simulated through the accelerated aging of these mock-ups that have the same chemical composition as the historical textiles. The aging process is monitored both colorimetrically and spectrally, while the full appearance attributes are captured using a total appearance capture device (TAC7). We then create a colour-based segmentation map over the 3D surface of the textiles to transfer the appearance of the mock-ups on the segmented regions. The fading simulations are further refined by tracing a correspondence in the spectral domain, between the mock-ups and the current appearance of the textiles. Lastly, we also harness available photographic documentation to speculate on the past colour and texture of the fugitive dyes in the textiles.

We embedded our appearance-aware fading simulations in an interactive application, entitled

Figure 24: Snapshots of the digitized 3D models of the kimono and Victorian dress (in the V&A collection).

Figure 25: The segmentation of fugitive colors in the UV-parameterized 3D model is achieved using a 2D parameterized atlas. This segmented atlas enables fading simulations and appearance-aware restoration of fugitive colors, guided by mockups, fading data, and reference images. Image source [41]

SimTex (**S**imulation of colour changes in **T**extiles), where the user can toggle between the current state of the two textiles and the three realistic scenarios for depicting the colour changes (see Fig.25 and 26), as follows:

1. **Mock-up Appearance:** This mode allows for the application of material maps from both aged and unaged mock-ups to the fugitive colors, facilitating appearance-aware construction.
2. **Spectral Unmixing:** This mode combines accelerated aging data from the mock-ups with spectral unmixing techniques, revealing the correlation between the fading of the mock-ups and the historical object. It is represented by texture images that illustrate a sequence of fading applied to the segmented fugitive colors.
3. **Photographic documentation:** This mode enables the application of textures from ref-

Figure 26: The figure above illustrates the three visualization modes available in the SimTex interactive visualization tool: Mock-up Appearance (left), where the material appearance from the mock-ups is directly transferred; Spectral Unmixing (middle), which simulates fading based on the current concentrations of the fugitive dyes; and Photographic Documentation (right), which utilizes colour data from various archival photographic records.

erence documentation images that depict the object in the past, allowing for visualization of potential restoration. The museum’s archive contains multiple digital images showcasing details of the kimono. The earliest image is from 2006 (front view), followed by one from 2019 (front view), and a 2024 capture that reveals the inner surface of the inner folds, previously shielded from light exposure. Additionally, there is a 2024 digital image of the inner surface of the Victorian dress.

The interactive apps for the two textiles can be found at the following permanent URLs: <https://perceive-tools.igd.fraunhofer.de/kimono/> and <https://perceive-tools.igd.fraunhofer.de/dress/>.

In the remainder of this sub-chapter, we will elaborate on all the stages in our methodology.

5.1 3D model capture and atlas-based segmentation

In this section, we describe our process for digitising the textiles in 3D and conducting automatic segmentation of the fugitive regions.

5.1.1 Photogrammetry Capture for 3D Model Generation:

The Victorian dress and the kimono (see Fig. 24) were positioned on a mannequin and a T-bar structure, respectively, within a photographic studio. Continuous halogen lights were employed, remaining fixed in their positions throughout the capture process to ensure consistent lighting. The lighting was kept soft and non-directional to minimize harsh shadows on the objects. A Sony Alpha 7 IV hybrid camera paired with a Sony 50mm f1.4 lens was utilized for the capture, ensuring over 60% overlap between images in both the x and y directions. The focus was set and maintained consistently throughout the entire capture process. Agisoft Metashape Professional software was used for image processing.

5.1.2 Atlas-Based Segmentation

The 3D modelling of the kimono and Victorian dress using photogrammetry provided us with a texture atlas for both textiles. A texture atlas is a single composite 2D image that packs multiple

sub-textures into one image file for efficient rendering. These sub-textures define the UV parameterization of a 3D surface by assigning each mesh vertex (x, y, z) specific UV coordinates (u, v) within the atlas. When the atlas additionally encodes semantic regions, it is referred to as a segmentation atlas.

To create the segmentation atlas, we apply segmentation in the HSV (Hue, Saturation, Value) colour space, with thresholding to identify and isolate the faded regions within the parameterized texture atlas, as exemplified in Fig. 27 for the kimono. For the i -th faded region, the thresholds are defined as $H_{min}^{(i)} \leq H \leq H_{max}^{(i)}$, $S_{min}^{(i)} \leq S \leq S_{max}^{(i)}$, and $V_{min}^{(i)} \leq V \leq V_{max}^{(i)}$ for hue, saturation, and value, respectively. The overall condition for segmenting a pixel in the i -th faded segment can be expressed as:

$$(H_{min}^{(i)} \leq H \leq H_{max}^{(i)}) \wedge (S_{min}^{(i)} \leq S \leq S_{max}^{(i)}) \wedge (V_{min}^{(i)} \leq V \leq V_{max}^{(i)}) \quad (6)$$

Figure 27: Segmentation atlas generation through HSV colour segmentation of the faded regions using various thresholds. Image source [41]

Finally, we developed a custom shader that utilized the UV-parametrized segmentation atlas to achieve the desired appearance for the various segments of the heritage garments.

5.1.3 Improved segmentation based on structural features

Segmenting fine-grained features is challenging when colours are similar or structures are very small. In our Victorian dress example, we therefore relied on structural features rather than colour alone. By registering those structural features to a reference atlas, we were able to isolate the faded purple (blue-labeled) and turquoise (red-labeled) regions (see Fig. 28). Although this method yields a partial segmentation of the dress, completing the full segmentation is left for future work where we intend to combine colour and structure-based segmentation.

5.2 Preparation of mockups

The textile mock-ups were prepared as representative models of the historic kimono and dress, designed to address the specific research questions of each case study with regards to their fading

Figure 28: Segmentation of the Victorian dress using structural features: (left) original atlas, (middle) registered features in the atlas, and (right) resulting partial segmentation when rendered in false-colour for a particular camera view (here blue represents faded purple and red the faded turquoise).

and to allow controlled experimentation without risking the original garments. By closely replicating materials, techniques, and visual appearance, the mock-ups provide a platform to study ageing and degradation under defined environmental conditions, particularly light exposure, offering crucial insights for preventive conservation.

The process began with detailed on-site, non-invasive analyses of each textile, including fibre identification, dye composition, and assessment of conservation state. These results guided the selection of historically accurate materials and dyeing techniques. Bibliographic documentation ensured that key variables such as mordanting methods, dye application sequences, and environmental history could be reproduced.

Once completed, the mock-ups were subjected to artificial photoaging under museum-specific lighting conditions. The exposure regimes replicated recorded lux levels, spectra, and durations from actual display periods, making the results directly applicable to the original artefacts. This approach enables prediction of material behaviour, investigation of degradation pathways, and evaluation of preventive conservation strategies in a reproducible, risk-free context.

Case Study: Myriad Green Leaves Kimono

The silk kimono, created in 1992 by the Japanese artist Furusawa Machiko, is part of the Victoria and Albert Museum’s textile collection (accession number FE.422-1992). It was crafted using shibori, a traditional Japanese resist-dyeing technique involving precise stitching, gathering, and binding to protect areas of fabric before successive dye applications. The dominant green hue was achieved through a two-step process: initial dyeing with yellow Kariyasu (*Miscanthus tinctorius*), followed by over-dyeing with indigo (*Indigofera tinctoria*), as recorded in the artist’s notes.

To replicate this textile, silk samples were prepared using artisanal dyeing methods with natural extracts of Kariyasu (yellow), indigo (blue), and a sequential application of both dyes to produce green. Both mordanted and non-mordanted fabrics were prepared to reflect possible historical variations in dyeing practice, as shown in Fig. 29. An undyed white silk control sample was also included for baseline measurements.

For artificial aging, one set of each colour (white, yellow, blue, and green) was stored in darkness as a reference, while the other set underwent 259 hours of controlled light exposure, simulating the

Figure 29: Left: The *Myriad Green Leaves* silk kimono (Furusawa Machiko, 1992), Victoria and Albert Museum (FE.422-1992). The layered dyeing process using Kariyasu and indigo produces the characteristic green hue. © Victoria and Albert Museum. Right: Silk mock-ups replicating the kimono's dye palette and methods, prepared for artificial aging tests.

Figure 30: Left: Victorian printed cotton dress (Edmund Potter & Co., 1887), Victoria and Albert Museum (T.2-1926), showing fading in the background. Right: Dyed cotton mock-ups prepared to match the original dress's colours, for use in artificial aging experiments.

museum's halogen and LED display conditions at 50 lux. Colour changes were measured periodically using colorimetry and reflectance spectroscopy, enabling the monitoring of fading and the detection of underlying chemical transformations.

Case Study: Victorian Printed Cotton Dress

The second case study focuses on a cotton dress printed by Edmund Potter & Co. in 1887, a leading calico printer of the 19th century (accession number T.2-1926). The design features a turquoise-blue background with motifs inspired by Japanese kamon and Indian chintz. Over time, sections of the fabric exposed to ambient light have faded markedly, while areas protected by folds retain most of their original brightness, as can be noticed in Fig. 30.

Material analysis suggests the use of early synthetic dyes from the triarylmethane family, common in late 19th-century textile production. To reproduce the dress's colour palette, cotton samples were mordanted and hand-dyed (see Fig. 30) with diamond green B (Basic Green 4, C.I. 42000), diamond green G (Basic Green 1, C.I. 42040), and yellowish light green SF (Acid Green 5, C.I. 42095). An undyed white cotton sample served as a control.

The dyed cotton mock-ups were subjected to 203 hours of artificial photoaging under outdoor light exposure. Regular spectroscopic measurements tracked the rate and nature of colour loss, permitting visual fading with chemical changes to be investigated in the synthetic dye molecules.

By combining historically faithful fabrication with controlled artificial aging, these mock-ups provide a reproducible way to evaluate how natural and synthetic dyes respond to photoaging

Figure 31: Appearance capture was conducted using TAC7 [24], and fitting to the appearance model was performed using Pantora [55] on the silk mockup of the kimono and the cotton mockup of the Victorian dress, both created by a conservation scientist.

under both indoor museum lighting and outdoor conditions, covering the full relevant spectral range from UV to visible light. The integration of analytical techniques both non-invasive and laboratory-based ensures a detailed understanding of degradation processes.

This methodology not only safeguards the original textiles but also produces data directly applicable to conservation decision-making, including the optimisation of lighting protocols and storage conditions. Ultimately, the study of these mock-ups contributes to the development of evidence-based preventive conservation strategies for both natural-dye and synthetic-dye textiles.

5.3 SVBRDF Capture and BRDF modelling

To accurately capture the SVBRDF of our mockup samples, we utilize the Total Appearance Capture (TAC7) [54, 24, 31], developed by X-Rite. This commercially available scanner is specifically designed for capturing material appearances and operates with Pantora software [55], which facilitates postprocessing and optional editing of the resulting SVBRDFs.

The TAC7 features a hemispherical array comprising 29 white LEDs and four monochrome cameras arranged in an arc above a rotating turntable. Five of the LEDs are equipped with colour filter wheels that include 10 filters covering the visible spectrum. To ensure detailed sampling of reflectance lobes, a linear light source can be rotated in the space above the sample holder. For each material analyzed, we gather 100 colour images, 348 monochrome point-lit images, and 280 linear light source images [30]. Additionally, a structured light projector is employed to capture low-resolution surface geometry, and transparent materials are illuminated from below using an LED that passes through a diffuser plate in the sample holder. The TAC7 generally requires about 30 minutes to process low-gloss anisotropic fabrics [30]. While it can detect fluorescence and alerts users to its presence, it does not incorporate fluorescence into the measurements; however, a mask can be used to identify sections of fluorescent fabric.

The captured appearance of textile mockups (kimono silk and Victorian dress) using the TAC7 device was used to extract the material maps with Pantora [55]. This software fits the appearance data to a spatially varying bidirectional reflectance distribution function (SVBRDF) and generates the corresponding material maps, as illustrated in Fig. 31. To the best of our knowledge, the fitting model provided by Pantora is regarded as state-of-the-art for achieving high-quality material fits. The anisotropic SVBRDF obtained from a TAC7 measurement consists of 13 channels: 3 channels for diffuse colour, 3 channels for normal maps, 3 channels for specular colour, 3 channels for anisotropic roughness, and 1 channel for Fresnel effects (see Fig. 31).

5.4 Fading simulation

Our approach to simulating colour fading relies on two main assumptions: either we have access to mockups that accurately replicate both the visual appearance and chemical composition of the dyes present in the studied textiles, and that are subjected to controlled accelerated aging, or we possess a series of visual records (photographics documentation) that document the objects' colours over time. The spectral reflectance measurements collected from the mockups at each stage of the accelerated aging process can be integrated with the appearance modeling framework outlined in the previous section, enabling a continuous simulation of colour changes in the textiles.

By measuring how light reflects off the surface of these mockups at different stages of aging, we can build a model that shows how the colours in the original textiles progresses throughout the aging timeline. This allows us to “rewind” the visual appearance of an object to its original state and then “play forward” its gradual fading, almost like watching a time-lapse of its life. This method presumes that the mockups fully and faithfully represent the appearance of the actual objects, which is rarely the case. As we can see in Fig. 32 and Fig. 33, the colours resulting from the direct appearance transfer from the mockups, although plausible, are rather saturated and vivid, in stark contrast with the real heritage object that is characterized by a natural patina and softer colours.

Figure 32: Past and future simulations of the kimono in Fig. 24, generated with direct appearance transfer from the mock-ups: unaged with reduced exposure (left), unaged as recorded by TAC7 (b), and aged as recorded by TAC7 (c). All renderings utilize a spotlight source with a colour temperature of 6600K.

To improve accuracy and convey a more natural looking effect, we compare the mock-ups' appearance with the current condition of the textiles using hyperspectral imaging. Thus, for each textile, we capture two details with a hyperspectral camera. The details were selected in such a way so that they contain the fugitive dyes in a good condition. With the spectral unmixing technique, we then break down the hyperspectral data into the constituent pure materials in the object, known as endmembers. For materials recreated as mock-ups, the spectral signatures of the endmembers are derived directly from the mock-ups; for those not represented by mock-ups, the signatures are extracted from the hyperspectral images themselves. Following spectral unmixing, we generate abundance maps that indicate the spatial distribution of each dye across the textile surface.

These maps can then be recombined with either aged or unaged spectral data from the mock-ups to simulate the fading process within the hyperspectral image, offering a dynamic and data-driven

Figure 33: Past and future simulations of the turquoise dye in the Victorian dress in Fig. 24 , generated with direct appearance transfer from representative mock-ups: unaged as recorded by TAC7 (a), and aged as recorded by TAC7 (b). Additionally, the faded violet regions have been rendered with a representative colour derived from analytical studies. All renderings utilize a spotlight source with a colour temperature of 6600K.

Figure 34: Dye abundance maps obtained with spectral unmixing from the hyperspectral images of the details in the Victorian dress.

Figure 35: Dye abundance maps obtained with spectral unmixing from the hyperspectral images of the details in the kimono .

visualization of colour degradation over time. For the Victorian dress, we first define the turquoise endmember with the spectral signature of the corresponding unaged mock-up (top row in Fig. 34). This is used for fading simulation from present to future. Then, in the bottom row, we extract the signature of the turquoise endmember from the hyperspectral image itself, as this dye is applied purely and unmixed. This is used for attempting to virtually restore the original colour in the dress.

The green in the kimono is a mixture of miscanthus and indigo, so we perform the unmixing

with the two spectra of the dyes taken from the unaged mock-ups. Because the detail scanned with HSI contains both green in good condition (in the top-central part) and faded green where indigo has severely depleted (left margin), we attempt the restoration of the past colors with former signal and the present to future discoloration with the latter signal. This simulation correlates any observed colour changes with actual chemical alterations, enabling a meaningful assessment of the progressive loss of colour that is directly linked to the behavior of the original materials. As a matter of fact, the simulations look more natural compared to the mock-up appearance mode, as can be noticed in Fig. 36 and 37.

Figure 36: Fading simulation for the kimono at various time intervals – hypothesized original colour (a) and fading expected in the future (b, c and d) – considering correlation of the mock-ups with the actual heritage clothings through spectral unmixing

Figure 37: Fading simulation for the turquoise dye in the Victorian dress at various time intervals – hypothesized original colour (left) and fading expected in the future (middle and right) – considering correlation of the mock-ups with the actual heritage clothings through spectral unmixing

The reconstruction of the kimono using photographic documentation (Fig. 38) reveals significant changes in color and detail from the front view in 2006 (a) to the front view in 2019 (b), highlighting the effects of time on its appearance. Likewise, the inner surface of the kimono (c), photographed in 2024, exhibits less fading compared to its current appearance captured in the 3D model (see Fig. 24), providing valuable insights into how the colors may have originally appeared. However, the reconstruction based on the reverse side of the kimono appears to be intermediate between the 2006 and 2019 reconstructions. This is expected, as the inner surface, although shielded from light exposure, likely experienced discoloration due to other untracked aging factors such as humidity and temperature affecting the inner folds. Similarly, when comparing the inner surface reconstruction of the Victorian dress (Fig. 38(d)) with its present-day appearance captured in the 3D model (Fig. 24), it is evident that the former is less faded than the latter.

Reconstructing color changes from chronologically archived photographs allows for retrospective modeling of degradation, offering important qualitative insights into the temporal evolution of dye fading and the long-term behavior of historic textile materials, though it does not provide

evidence of the environmental factors influencing color alterations. A significant limitation of using documentation pictures taken over various years is the ambiguity introduced by subjective choices in photography, such as differing view and illumination setups, as well as potential variations in post-processing and color calibration pipelines.

Figure 38: Reconstruction of the kimono’s historical colors using reference documentation images shown in the top corners: (a) from 2006, (b) from 2019 and (c) depicting the inner surface of the kimono that was shielded from light exposure. Also included is the Victorian dress (d) based on a photograph from the inner surface. All images are illuminated with a spotlight set to a colour temperature of 6600K

5.5 Multi-light image collection modelling of the Burse, Purse and Pin-cushion

Several objects at the Victoria and Albert Museum, displayed in Figure 39, were captured with the Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI) photographic method, where the camera and object are kept static while the position of the incident light is moved in a dome-like configuration on top of the object. This technique outputs a so-called multi-light image collection (MLIC), where for every pixel in the colour images, you get a light-varying profile. A MLIC can be fitted with various appearance models, that reveal appearance attributes of the object (such as normal, albedo), and facilitate the relighting of the objects from unmeasured light positions. The ultimate purpose of fitting these image sets with various appearance models is to find distinctive features for the metallic threads that could later help in segmenting and restoring them.

Multiple MLIC fitting algorithms were tested using the Relight software [36], including LPTM- Polynomial Texture Map [29] fitted in the luminance domain, PTM- Polynomial Texture Mapping fitted on each of the R, G, B colour channels, HSH12- Hemispherical Harmonics [17] for luminance data, HSH27- Hemispherical Harmonics in the colour domain, BLN - Bilinear interpolation in the colour domain, YBLN- Bilinear interpolation in the luminance domain, RBF-Radial Basis Function interpolation [18, 16] in the colour domain, and YRBF- RBF in the luminance domain. After generating the various models, the reconstructed images were compared to the original input images, by computing the pixelwise average CIEDE2000 colour difference, reported in Table 2.

A significant challenge encountered was the desaturation of RTIs compared to the input images (see Figure 40). Various methods were explored to troubleshoot this issue, including leave-one-out comparisons and the exclusion of shadow-heavy images from the dataset. Despite these efforts, the desaturation issue remained unresolved, indicating a potential limitation of the Relight software [36]. This needs to be explored further by using alternative software for the modelling of the image sets. Moreover, other appearance models such as BRDF should be included for the fitting.

Figure 39: Left: Burse(1558-1603), inventory number T.40 1986. Right: Purse and pincushion (1600-1625), inventory numbers T.52 1954 and T.52A 1954

Figure 40: Original image (left) and reconstructed image with BLN (right).

Table 2: Comparison of 5 MLIC appearance fitting models, based on colour difference. Average ΔE_{00} is reported for each image set, computed by first averaging the pixel-by-pixel colour differences between each input image and modelled image at each light position, then averaging those results across the entire image set.

Imageset	Bilinear	LPTM	PTM	RBF	YRBF
T.40 1986 Back	2.86	3.61	3.52	2.49	7.23
T.40 1986 Front	4.81	5.05	4.96	4.20	6.10
T.52 1954 Back	5.41	6.72	6.59	4.99	5.22
T.52 1954 Front	5.57	7.10	6.91	4.95	5.14
T.52A 1954 Back	4.56	6.21	6.14	4.07	4.05
T.52A 1954 Front	4.37	5.78	5.68	4.05	4.02

6 Modelling colour change in historical photo / film collections

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The investigation of the deterioration of autochromes and Kodacolor films and the reconstruction of their original appearance are essential to appreciate the full scope and impact of these pioneering colour processes. While these early technologies represent significant milestones in the history of photography and cinematography, their unique aesthetic qualities are often lost due to their inherent fragility, chemical instability and physical degradation.

By digitally reconstructing their original colours and appearance, we make it possible for the general public to experience these works as they were intended—vivid, immersive, and historically rich—thereby fostering greater appreciation and enjoyment of early colour imaging, its cultural significance and its societal impact.

An introduction to autochromes

The Autochrome Lumière is considered the first commercially successful colour photography process. Publicly released in 1907, the invention by the Lumière Brothers was publicly praised for its production of luminous colour photographs. Autochromes comprise a glass plate, on top of which sits thousands of starch granules dyed red, green and blue, which act as a colour filter. On top of the colour filter is a layer of panchromatic silver emulsion. In essence, the colour filter produces the impression of colour in the photograph, while the silver gelatin emulsion provides the image, or outline.

Autochromes were used primarily in the period 1907 to 1930. During this time, multiple problems with the process became apparent, particularly in regards to the presentation and preservation of colour. Articles in photographic journals from the period discuss the presence of issues including 'greening', which manifest on the autochrome plate as small spots or large areas in shades of green. Other issues included the presence of orange areas or spots on the plate, silvering and, more commonly, the fading of colours. Autochromes were found to be extremely light sensitive, and popular means of exhibiting glass plates in the period like projection caused the colour dyes to quickly fade. Articles dating from the early twentieth century discuss limiting projection and

the light exposure of plates to mere seconds to avoid fading as well as the potential melting of the photographic emulsion.

Today, as well as in the early twentieth century, it was understood that when the colour in autochromes changed or was damaged, there was little action that could be taken to restore the plates to their original appearance. PERCEIVE has worked on new initiatives that offer means to generate an image which provides a sense of what the autochrome may have originally appeared like.

An introduction to Kodacolor

Since the emergence of cinema in the 1890s, inventors and researchers sought ways to bring colour photography into motion pictures. However, it took decades before a workable method of recording colour in film was achieved. The lenticular process offered a solution by capturing three colour separations simultaneously within a single film frame. The principles behind this technique originated from earlier work by pioneers such as Liesegang and Lippmann. Liesegang had imagined a pixelated approach using a perforated screen, while Lippmann described in detail the use of lenticular film to achieve more realistic colour reproduction [34]. In the early 1900s, Berthon built upon these ideas and applied them to moving pictures [3]. It took a long time before Kodak managed to refine and commercialise the technology quickly, launching Kodacolor in 1928 as a 16mm reversal film designed for amateur use. For any new colour process to thrive, it needed widespread adoption, compatibility with existing recording and projection equipment, and the ability to produce distributable copies. Kodacolor struggled in the latter area. Moreover, it suffered from the common drawbacks of additive colour methods, including low image brightness, reduced sharpness, and a limited colour range. Although Kodacolor enjoyed some popularity among amateur filmmakers, its appeal quickly faded when Kodak introduced Kodachrome, and lenticular film disappeared by the late 1930s.

Today, many lenticular films remain hidden or misidentified, as they appear to be ordinary black-and-white reels at first glance. Raising awareness of these films is crucial to ensure their proper identification, preservation, and eventual rediscovery for future generations.

6.1 Modelling colour change in autochromes

We present two distinct methodologies for the colour restoration of autochromes, both of which follow a shared processing pipeline illustrated in Figure 41, previously published in [9]. This pipeline begins with the separation of the colour mosaic from the silver emulsion and proceeds by replacing the silver-decoupled dyes with unfaded reference dyes to achieve colour restoration. The key difference between the two approaches lies in the strategy employed for silver/dye separation. In this section, we will only focus on one method: spectral unmixing. For more details about the imaging set-up and silver/dye separation, please refer to the original publication.

This method capitalizes on the spectral resolution capabilities of our imaging system by formulating the silver/dye separation as a spectral unmixing problem. Following the unmixing process, we replace the spectral signatures of the degraded dyes in the dye mosaic with those of unfaded reference dyes. The restored colour mosaic is then recombined with the silver emulsion. To the best of our knowledge, this represents the first application of spectral unmixing techniques to the restoration of autochromes.

Figure 41: Our restoration pipeline is defined by the processing of the colour mosaic after its uncoupling from the silver emulsion layer.

6.1.1 Test autochromes

The significant light sensitivity of autochromes means that many museums choose to limit public access and restrict exhibiting original plates. To avoid degradation on autochromes from public collections, we purchased four autochromes from antiques sites and private collectors for the purpose of the project, each exhibiting varying degrees of fading and typical deterioration such as greening (Fig 42).

6.1.2 High resolution multispectral image capture

To capture the fine structural and spectral details of autochromes, we employed a high-magnification multispectral imaging system. Autochromes are composed of microscopic dyed potato starch granules, each approximately $10\ \mu\text{m}$ in diameter. To resolve individual granules, our system achieves a spatial resolution of $1.84\ \mu\text{m}$ on the object plane, enabling precise analysis of the colour mosaic.

The imaging setup is a modified version of the active multispectral system described in [48], consisting of a monochrome 16-bit CCD camera paired with a $5\times$ magnification lens (Fig. 43a). Illumination is provided by an integrating sphere equipped with ten LEDs, each emitting at distinct spectral peaks in the visible spectrum.

To ensure uniform illumination, the light from the integrating sphere is collimated using a condenser lens and diffused through a translucent slab, creating a bright-field setup. The autochrome plate is placed on a custom holder with a black cover (Fig. 43b), exposing only the area being imaged to minimize stray light and reduce unnecessary exposure. The holder is mounted on an XYZ translation stage, allowing for precise positioning and tile-based image acquisition, which can later be stitched into a complete image.

Exposure times are optimized individually for each spectral band to maximize the dynamic range of the 16-bit sensor without saturation. Due to the inherently low transmittance of autochrome

glass plates [19], we use a neutral density (ND) filter with 0.4 optical density as the white reference, rather than an empty gate. Each captured image undergoes flat-field and dark-current correction.

Given the extreme light sensitivity of autochromes, we also assessed the potential impact of our imaging process on material degradation. This monitoring enables us to compare current and future captures, providing a framework to evaluate any fading induced by the digitization process.

(a) Couple by the lake. Autochrome used by permission of the collector, Arthur Clay.

(b) Gruyere, 1914

(c) Harrogate shop window

(d) Poppy field

(e) Umbrella. Autochrome used by permission of the collector, Arthur Clay.

Figure 42: Test autochromes acquired for this research. (Images not to scale)

(a) Multispectral Imaging Setup.

(b) Setup closeup - Autochrome plate on holder, with black cover to minimize stray light and exposure.

Figure 43: Our autochrome digitization setup is non-invasive and offers flexibility in adjusting the distance between the photograph and the camera.

6.1.3 Spectral unmixing

In our spectral unmixing approach to autochrome restoration, we treat the three dyes—red-orange (R), green (G), and blue-violet (B)—as endmembers. Silver and carbon, which primarily modulate image contrast rather than contribute distinct spectral signatures, are captured in the residuals of the unmixing model. This rationale allows us to focus on separating the dye components from the monochromatic signals introduced by silver and carbon.

For each autochrome, we construct a multispectral image cube using only the bands within the visible spectrum. To identify the spectral signatures of the dyes, we select a region of the image that is free from silver interference. Within this no-silver area, we sample the spectra of individual dye granules and average them to obtain representative spectral profiles for each dye’s optical density.

Operating in the additive absorption domain, we assume a linear spectral mixing model. That

is, each pixel ij in the multispectral cube is considered a linear combination of the three dye endmembers:

$$OD_{cube} = ab_R^{ij} * OD_R + ab_G^{ij} * OD_G + ab_B^{ij} * OD_B + residual^{ij} \quad (7)$$

with $i = 1..N$ and $j = 1..M$, where N is the number of rows and M is the number of columns in the multispectral image. This assumption simplifies the unmixing process and enables us to estimate the spatial abundance of each dye across the image, forming the basis for accurate colour restoration.

The objective of the spectral unmixing process is to estimate the abundance ab of each dye at every pixel (i, j) in the multispectral image cube. These abundance values represent the spatial distribution of each dye across the image, forming what is known as an abundance map. While abundance is proportional to dye concentration, it does not correspond to absolute quantities and lacks a standardized unit of measurement.

To compute the abundance maps, we solve the linear mixing model using a least-squares minimization approach [23]. The optimization minimizes the squared difference between the observed multispectral cube and its reconstruction based on the linear combination of the dye endmembers:

$$|OD_{cube} - \widehat{OD}_{cube}|^2$$

This minimization is subject to the constraint that all abundance values remain non-negative, ensuring physical plausibility. The resulting abundance maps provide a robust estimate of the spatial presence of each dye, enabling accurate colour restoration while implicitly accounting for the influence of silver and carbon through the residuals of the model.

Once the abundance maps for each dye are computed, we reconstruct the multispectral image cube by multiplying these maps with the corresponding spectral signatures of the dyes:

$$\widehat{OD}_{cube} = ab_R^{ij} * OD_R + ab_G^{ij} * OD_G + ab_B^{ij} * OD_B. \quad (8)$$

This yields a modelled version of the original multispectral cube, representing the contribution of the dye mosaic alone.

The residual error is then calculated as the difference between the original multispectral cube and the reconstructed cube:

$$residual^{ij} = OD_{cube} - \widehat{OD}_{cube} \quad (9)$$

This residual captures the spectral information not explained by the dye components—primarily the influence of the silver emulsion and carbon elements. In this way, the abundance maps effectively isolate the spatial distribution of the dyes, while the residual serves as a segmentation of the silver layer and other non-dye components.

6.1.4 Colour restoration

To restore the original colours of the autochrome dyes, we rely on the spectral transmittance measurements of unfaded dyes previously obtained by Lavédrine and Gandolfo [26] from a well-preserved historical autochrome. These spectral profiles represent the optical characteristics of the red-orange, green, and blue-violet dyes used to colour the potato starch granules.

Using the spectral unmixing approach, we decompose the multispectral cube of each autochrome into abundance maps for the three dyes, as described by Equation 7. Faded dyes typically exhibit lower and flatter optical density curves compared to their unfaded counterparts. To reconstruct the unfaded appearance, we multiply the abundance maps by the reference optical densities of the unfaded dyes, resulting in a restored colour mosaic.

Figure 44: Left: Dyes uncovered by the silver emulsion, cropped from the colour image of the autochrome Couple by the lake. Right: Spectral signatures of the pure dyes in the “Couple by the lake” autochrome

To reintroduce spatial detail, we add the residual component which captures the silver and carbon contributions back to the restored mosaic. This yields the final restored multispectral cube, expressed as:

$$OD_{restored\ cube} = ab_R^{ij} * OD_{Ref\ R} + ab_G^{ij} * OD_{Ref\ G} + ab_B^{ij} * OD_{Ref\ B} + residual^{ij} \quad (10)$$

The restored cube is then rendered using the CIE 1931 22° standard observer and the D50 standard illuminant. For final image encoding, we apply the Rec. 2020 colour profile, which follows the ITU-R BT.1886 [39] recommendation and includes gamma encoding with $\gamma = 1/2.4$.

6.1.5 Colour restoration of partially faded autochromes

The test autochromes were imaged using the high-resolution multispectral setup previously described. Figure 44 presents a selected area from each autochrome where the silver emulsion is assumed to be transparent, shown at 100% magnification. The spatial resolution of the imaging system is sufficient to resolve individual dyed starch granules, allowing for a detailed assessment of their current state of conservation. The optical densities of the dyes were computed by averaging pixel values within the selected area shown in Figure 44. Compared to the reference optical densities of autochromes, the faded dyes exhibit lower maximum densities, indicating reduced light absorption, and higher minimum densities indicating reduced light transmission. This dual effect results in diminished contrast and desaturated colours, characteristic of aged autochromes.

For each autochrome in our study, we selected a region devoid of silver emulsion which served as the basis for extracting the average spectral signatures of the red, green, and blue dyes within the visible range 44. These spectral profiles were used as endmembers in the spectral unmixing method, allowing us to compute the spatial distribution of each dye across the entire image in the form of abundance maps.

Beyond dye separation, we also decomposed the silver and carbon signals. Because carbon is optically mixed with the adjacent dyes, its contribution is embedded within the abundance maps.

The silver layer, however, is isolated by calculating the residual between the original multispectral image and the image reconstructed using the unmixing model.

To reconstruct the original multispectral cube, we multiply the abundance maps by their corresponding endmember spectra, accounting only for the dyes and carbon elements. The resulting colour rendering of the faded dye mosaic is shown in Fig. 45b. Similar to the band subtraction method, a faint ghost-like artefact of the woman’s silhouette is visible, likely due to scattering effects not captured by our current model.

For the virtual restoration, we replace the faded dye spectra with the reference spectra of unfaded dyes, combining them with the abundance maps to generate a restored dye mosaic (Fig. 45d). Finally, we add the silver layer, represented by the residual image (Fig. 45e) to the restored dye mosaic, producing the fully restored autochrome shown in Fig. 45c.

6.1.6 Colour restoration of autochromes with completely faded blue dye

The autochromes previously discussed exhibit varying degrees of fading across their dyes. In this subsection, we focus on a particularly degraded autochrome in which the blue-violet dye has completely faded, namely the “Umbrella” autochrome shown in Fig. 42e. Figure 46 shows a magnified view (100%) of its dyed potato starch granules, revealing that the blue dye granules are nearly transparent, while only the red-orange and green dyes remain visibly present. Further analysis of the spectral curves confirms this observation: not only is the blue dye absent, but the remaining red and green dyes also show significant fading. Their optical density curves are both flattened and reduced in magnitude, indicating diminished absorption and transmission properties. This results in a severely desaturated colour mosaic with low contrast, characteristic of advanced dye degradation in autochromes.

In this particular case of advanced degradation, the autochrome exhibited such severe fading that the band subtraction method was no longer viable. The optical densities of the dyes were too similar and too diminished to allow for meaningful separation, rendering the method ineffective. Instead, we applied the spectral unmixing approach, following the same procedure outlined in previous sections. We extracted the spectral signatures of the faded dyes directly from silver-free regions of the image. This allowed us to estimate the spatial distribution of the remaining dye components through abundance maps, even under conditions of extreme fading. Although the spectral contrast between the dyes was minimal, the unmixing method proved sufficiently robust to isolate the residual dye information, as shown in Fig. 47. The resulting abundance maps enabled us to reconstruct the faded dye mosaic and proceed with virtual restoration, despite the near-complete loss of the blue-violet dye and the significant fading of the red-orange and green dyes.

To capture the full extent of the umbrella depicted in the autochrome and to produce a visually compelling result, we created a mosaic composed of 45 individual acquisitions. This approach allowed us to preserve fine spatial detail across the entire image while also enhancing its aesthetic impact. The resulting stitched image not only showcases the intricate structure of the dyed starch granules when zoomed in, but also serves as a striking visual demonstration of the restoration process. By presenting both the original and restored versions, the image effectively illustrates the transformative effect of our method and highlights the contrast between the faded and unfaded colour mosaics.

Figure 45: The restoration with the spectral unmixing method (c) pulls up the faded blue colours in the original image, obvious especially in the coat area, and increases the overall contrast. Moreover, the dyes are well decoupled from the silver layer. The restoration is sharper, as the spectral unmixing denoises the image through dimensionality reduction. This is particularly obvious if we compare the silver layer (f) as given by infrared image (that has several artifacts and is affected by blurriness) with the residual of the spectral unmixing (e).

Figure 46: Left: Dyes uncovered by the silver emulsion, cropped from the colour image of the autochrome “Umbrella”. Right: Spectral signatures of the pure dyes in the “Umbrella” autochrome

Figure 47: The “Umbrella” autochrome has no blue colours, because the blue dye has faded completely to the point of becoming white. For this reason, its restoration is more dramatic than in the case of the other autochromes. Apart from the blue dye, the red and green are also rather desaturated, more so than in the other test autochromes.

Figure 48: The full umbrella (as result of stitching 45 captured images) detail in the “Umbrella” autochrome, split between its current, faded state (left side of the diagonal), and the restoration with the spectral unmixing method (right side of the diagonal). We can notice how the umbrella regains not only its blue, bleached in the current state, but also the vividness of its red and green colours. The two magnifier peepholes illustrate the full resolution of the colour granules in the autochrome’s mosaic. At this resolution, it is even more obvious how the blue dye has bleached completely becoming white. At the same time, albeit not completely faded, the red and green granules have a very low saturation with respect to the original dyes.

Figure 49: Examples of real greening defects: small area or spotting defects (left) and large area defects (right). Image source [46]

6.2 Neural restoration of greening defects in autochrome photograph utilizing purely synthetic data

The Autochrome Lumière, introduced in 1907, is recognized as the first commercially successful color photography process, making it a significant invention in the history of photography. Autochrome plates are made up of a silver gelatin layer that forms the image and a color filter layer that determines the colors seen in the photographic plate. This color filter layer contains thousands of tiny potato starch granules dyed red, green, and blue. The autochrome remained in use until the early 1930s, when it was replaced by Kodachrome technologies. Today we recognize that autochromes are extremely fragile and light sensitive, making them prone to color changes, like fading, and damage due to issues such as greening and orange spotting. Once autochromes exhibit colour changes, like fading or green spotting, this damage cannot be repaired.

"Greening" and green spotting (see Figure 49) are characterized by green areas or spots on the autochrome plate. The historical dyes used to color the starch granules in autochromes are sensitive to water. The green dye, in particular, is vulnerable and can bleed into other areas of the image if moisture penetrates the plate, leading to the greening defect. In severe cases, the entire image can become unreadable.

Since this damage cannot be reversed in physical autochrome plates, Sinha et.al [42] proposed using AI models to digitally restore images of digitized autochromes that exhibit greening. To train these AI models for image restoration, we first need to simulate the greening defect, which is referred to as a synthetic defect. The next section describes how we synthetic greening defects [42] were generated.

6.2.1 Synthetic greening defect generation

To address the key issue of insufficient datasets for damaged autochromes, Sinha et al. [42] proposed a method for generating a synthetic dataset suitable for training and testing autochrome restoration techniques. To ensure the quality of this synthetic dataset, we conducted a thorough analysis of

Figure 50: Synthetic greening defects (small area (left) and large area (right) defect) generated using the approach proposed by Sinha et.al. [42]. Image source [46]

actual defects found in autochromes. This analysis revealed that defects can be classified as spot-shaped, widespread, a combination of both, or resulting in complete image loss. We selected seven autochromes for a more detailed evaluation, which demonstrated that spot defects typically range from 1% to 5% of the overall image width, while larger defects can occur independently, covering up to one-third of the image. However, the merging of larger area defects with other spot defects is relatively rare.

In an initially generated dataset, defects were simulated using color filters commonly employed in photography, with a particular focus on green filters to represent the foreground layer during the defect generation for the autochrome in the background layer. However, this approach ultimately failed to produce realistic results, as the defects exhibited low color variance, rendering them unrealistic. Hence, a second dataset was created, referred to as ChannelGreeningDefects (see Figure 50), which directly captures observable changes in the color channels within the defective areas. The process of generating this synthetic defects [42] can be described below:

- Images may contain point defects (60%), large defects (30%), or both (10%), with defect masks generated according to the characteristics of these known defects. These masks are created with 1 to 7 spot-shaped defects or 1 to 2 larger defects, using sizes and centers defined based on known size ratios from real defects.
- The generation of area and spot-shaped defects involves creating ellipses distorted by random radius adjustments at their boundaries. Spot defects have their centers located within the image, resulting in point-shaped origins, while large area defects are represented by significantly larger ellipses with origins outside the image, simulating the leakage of liquids that penetrate the autochrome and cause damage. The parametric equations [42] for the ellipse are given by:

$$x(t) = x_c + a \cdot \cos(t) \cdot \text{irregularity},$$

$$y(t) = y_c + b \cdot \sin(t) \cdot \text{irregularity},$$

where (x_c, y_c) are the coordinates of the center of the ellipse, (a, b) are the semi-major and semi-minor axis lengths, t is an angular parameter in $[0, 2\pi]$, and irregularity is a factor affecting the shape of the ellipse. The center of defect masks may be point-shaped or linear, and the intensity of the defect is interpolated based on the normalized distance d to the origin, with a decrease in intensity computed by $I = -d^2 + 1$.

- For each ring, a change in the percentage of the individual color channels in the defect areas is defined, randomly adjusted by a factor of 0.2 (chosen empirically to avoid drastic changes and maintain the realism of the defects) in both directions for each image. The combined defect pattern is smoothed using a Gaussian filter, and the intensity change ΔI_c for color channel c is calculated as $\Delta I_c = (p_c * I_c) - I_c$, where p_c is the corruption percentage. This change is then applied to the final image. Table 3 shows the definition of the individual modifications per channel and ring in a dictionary.

Label	Blue	Green	Red	Effect in defect
9	0.6	0.85	1.05	Outer orange ring
1	0.5	1.2	0.8	Light green ring
2	0.4	0.8	0.6	Middle
3	0.4	0.8	0.6	Middle
4	0.2	0.6	0.1	Dark green second
99	0.2	0.2	0.1	Dark mid
20	0.4	0.95	0.6	Surface

Table 3: Dictionary for ring of corruption. Source [42]

6.2.2 Training of restoration network

Image2Image models, specifically Pix2Pix [21] and CycleGAN [56], were trained on the synthetic defect dataset (see Figure 50) using the original training configurations. However, these approaches did not yield satisfactory results in restoring the original colors of the defective areas, as they modified the images without effectively addressing the restoration task. Therefore, the ChaIR (Channel Interactions for Image Restoration) model [12] was selected due to its demonstrated state-of-the-art performance in deraining and dehazing tasks which is similar to our problem. This model utilizes spatial and frequency loss functions to evaluate performance and supports dual-channel attention mechanisms. While it primarily affected the greening regions, it showed promise in its application despite the challenges in overall color restoration. The main challenge for autochrome restoration remains the accurate representation of the original colors in the defective areas. To enhance the restoration process, a modified loss function was implemented [42], prioritizing the impact on defective areas over non-defective regions.

A further step involved the digital in-painting of autochromes which have had been de-greened. When digitally restored, the de-greened area can appear pale or off-colour. Using hundreds of

Figure 51: Large area greening defects removal utilizing the approach proposed by Sinha et.al [42]. Image source [46]

Figure 52: Large area greening defects (with significant damage) removal utilizing the approach proposed by Sinha et.al [42]. Image source [46]

undamaged autochromes, we trained the network [25] utilizing low rank adaptation (LoRA) [20] to understand the unique colour palette and texture of the autochrome. Based on this training, the network is able to inpaint those areas digitally “de-greened” so that they more closely resemble the colour and texture of an autochrome (see Figure 53).

6.2.3 Results

Figure 51 shows that large area defects are removed utilizing this de-greening model. The greening is significantly reduced and this improves the state-of-the-art image restoration methods as evaluated and shown by the work presented by Sinha et. al. [42]. Moreover, even greening defects with significant could be removed partially as shown in Figure 52. In terms of small area defects (green spotting) the de-greened output followed by inpainting using a finetuned model [25] could produce perceptually restored results as shown in Figure 53. This approach was most effective in stationary regions—areas within an image where statistical properties such as texture, color, and intensity

Figure 53: Removal of small area greening defects (left) using the approach proposed by Sinha et al.[42] (middle), followed by inpainting with a fine-tuned model[25] that employs Low Rank Adaptation [20] (right). Image source [46]

remain relatively constant. This concept is closely linked to stationary texture, which refers to a uniform and consistent pattern throughout a given area.

6.2.4 Final comments

The proposed method effectively identifies and removes some greening defects in old autochrome photographs, regardless of their size or location. By adjusting the colors in the affected areas, the method makes these defects less noticeable. However, it sometimes struggles to accurately reproduce the original colors of the autochrome images, which can lead to bluish tones and the omission of very small defects. To enhance the restoration process, AI-based inpainting methods has been employed to selectively remove small defects using the mask and the de-greened output predicted by the model.

The results of this method can improve editing tools, allowing designers to efficiently achieve similar outcomes while tackling defects that are otherwise difficult to manage, especially in larger areas. Future efforts should aim to expand the synthetic dataset to include digitized autochromes from various collections and to identify effective no-reference metrics—tools that assess image quality without needing a reference image for comparison. These advancements would enable a more comprehensive evaluation of restoration quality across a diverse array of samples. Moreover, the techniques developed could be adapted to address other autochrome defects, such as orangening, and could also be applied to restore various types of artworks and images, broadening their impact in the field of image restoration.

6.3 Reconstructing colour in Kodacolor films

6.3.1 Technical specifications

Lenticular Kodacolor used a form of spatial encoding to capture colour information. The 16 mm film base was embossed with hundreds of fine vertical cylindrical lenses. On the reverse side, a black-and-white panchromatic silver emulsion recorded the image. Figure 54 schematically illustrates the

photographic process. During film shooting (left), a special red-green-blue filter (tripartite filter) was placed in front of the camera lens. The lenticular surface focused each colour component onto the emulsion as narrow vertical stripes, enabling colour scenes to be captured on black-and-white film stock. Reversal processing produced a positive silver-based image.

Figure 54: Schematic illustration of the optical principle underlying image capture and visualization in lenticular colour film, considering a green-yellow-red flag as photographed object.

The projection (right) required a complementary setup: a projector fitted with a matching red-green-blue filter. When projected, the magnified images recombined to form a full-colour picture on the screen. However, this method of display has since become obsolete. Today, preserving and recovering Kodacolor films requires addressing this issue of technological obsolescence.

6.3.2 Digitisation and colour reconstruction

Digitising Kodacolor films provides a practical way to make these works accessible to the public while also safeguarding them against the inevitable decay of the original film material. Several approaches can be used to extract the embedded colour information. Four main methods can be outlined:

- **Telecine** - This is the most straightforward solution. The original projection system, equipped with the red-green-blue filter, is used, and a digital video camera records the projected colour image on the screen. A synchronization mechanism is required to align the frame rate of the film projector with that of the digital capture device.
- **Colour Digital Capture** - Instead of projecting the image onto a screen (like in "telecine"), a dedicated imaging system can be employed. A lens equipped with a red-green-blue filter—equivalent to the original one—focuses the colour image directly onto a digital colour sensor

at low magnification. This process involves frame-by-frame sequential capture using a film transport system.

- **Slit-Scan Capture** - Based on the same principle as *colour digital capture*, the slit-scan eliminates the use of a red-green-blue filter and employs a monochrome digital sensor. A moving slit in front of the lens isolates a specific angular portion of the light, enabling the capture of a single colour component at a time. Three successive exposures per frame, with the slit positioned differently each time, provide the complete colour information. The film transport system is intermittent.
- **Digital Decoding** - In this approach, the film is scanned at high resolution (at 15 or more pixels per lenticule horizontally) with the emulsion facing the imaging system so that the encoded silver-based colour components remain in focus. Specialised software then reconstructs the colour image by:
 1. Locating the lenticular screen, and
 2. Converting the side-by-side silver densities into RGB values.

Among the four methods, *telecine* depends on original Kodacolor projection equipment, which is now extremely rare. Both *colour digital capture* and *slit-scan capture* demand highly specialised, custom-built devices, making them impractical for most institutions. By contrast, *digital decoding* can be considered the most efficient and widely applicable solution. It requires only a conventional high-resolution film scanner for image acquisition, while the reconstruction of the colour information is carried out entirely in software. In 2013, two independent research groups validated the digital decoding approach: Reuteler, Fornaro, and Gschwind within the SNF project doLCE at the University of Basel [37], and Aschenbach in a separate study [2]. The PERCEIVE project draws on the work of Reuteler and Gschwind and on the later advances by D’Aronco and colleagues [13]. The central challenge in digital decoding lies in accurately locating the lenticular screen. The original doLCE method relied on signal processing: it averaged the image rows, then identified the local minima of the pixel value profile to determine the screen’s structure. The more recent deep-doLCE approach replaced this strategy with a deep-learning framework. Rather than fine-tuning the existing algorithm with additional parameters, it sought higher robustness and accuracy by letting a neural network learn the structure of the lenticular pattern directly from data.

6.3.3 doLCE 2.0

Despite the improvement in some cases, deep-doLCE still failed to properly reconstruct some films, therefore, under the auspices of PERCEIVE, the research into this topic has continued. The work focused on a 1930 travelogue to the Norwegian fjords filmed by the amateur filmmaker Arnold Hennings. This 16mm movie is a combination of tinted film (title cards), black-and-white (most of the content), and lenticular Kodacolor (last part). The colour reconstruction using deep-doLCE resulted in image frames that introduced their own set of problems. Many frames displayed artifacts and, in several cases, completely incorrect colours. This issue arises from the lenticule detection model’s inability to accurately predict lenticular borders for the provided image set. To improve the colour reconstruction of the travelogue, we refined the original deep-doLCE model using more representative training data aligned with the lenticular boundaries of the scans. This finetuning step enabled the model to more accurately detect boundaries and thereby achieve more reliable colour reproduction. To build this dataset, we employed a semi-automatic labelling process supported by visual analysis, ensuring that reconstructed colours were both technically consistent and historically

plausible (e.g., skies appeared bluish, grass greenish, and clothing matched known period tones). We explored two complementary strategies for generating representative data:

- Manual refinement of lenticular boundaries. First, we applied the original deep-doLCE model to colourize the full video sequence. We then selected frames at intervals where colours appeared reasonably plausible. Using these as a starting point, we manually corrected the detected lenticular boundaries to improve accuracy. The corrected frames formed the training data for finetuning the model. If results remained unsatisfactory, additional frames were labelled and incorporated, with the process repeated iteratively until the reconstructed sequence achieved a visually consistent and credible colour balance.
- Automatic selection of plausible frames. To reduce manual intervention, we also adopted a more automated strategy. Instead of adjusting boundaries directly, we identified frames or cropped regions where the original model’s output already showed convincing colours. These selections, validated through visual reasoning, were then used to finetune the model. As with the manual approach, additional data were added iteratively until the sequence produced stable and realistic colour results.

Together, these methods demonstrate that user-guided finetuning—whether through manual adjustment or selective frame validation—can substantially improve the colour reconstruction of lenticular film scans, even when source material is of suboptimal quality.

7 Conclusion and discussion

This is the final version of the Deliverable 3.2, which aims to present and discuss the general approach in the PERCEIVE project to the use of colour and material appearance models to enable simulation, rendering, regeneration or prediction in the tools being developed to improve the digital representation of coloured heritage objects and to address the digital reconstruction of the appearance of the objects over time, as proposed in the PERCEIVE scenarios. A general systematic approach was followed for all models, combining empirical evidence from available collected and experimental data, theoretical foundations, data augmentation based on assumptions, computational simulations and iterative testing.

At the foundation of most proposed models are well-designed mock-ups that embody the chemistry and stratigraphy of historical practices—whether Punic-wax polychromy on Pentelic/Parian marble, pigments with linseed oil in paintings, or natural/synthetic dyes on silk and cotton. Colour and spectral imaging, together with appearance capture (MA-T12, TAC7) and SVBRDF/AxF modelling preserve colour, spectral and geometric cues (diffuse, specular, normals, roughness), supporting photorealistic rendering of instances of the studied artworks in past and future.

For classical sculptures, an atlas-based segmentation and semantic shading framework enabled the transfer of measured material models from controlled mock-ups onto segmented 3D reconstructions, overcoming earlier “flat colour” restorations by recovering gloss, texture, and micro-geometry cues essential to perceived authenticity of polychromy.

For paintings, we showed that complementary strategies - (i) a mechanistic photochemical model that ties ΔL^* , Δa^* , and Δb^* trajectories to spectral radiant exposure and (ii) spectral unmixing operating in absorbance space - yield predictive maps and renderings of future damage, while historical photographic records can be corrected (via dye density balancing and learned film→painting transforms) to approximate past appearances. This pluralistic approach reduced

the typical “lack-of-ground-truth” problem by cross-validating expected behaviours (e.g. vermilion darkening, cadmium yellow fading).

For textiles, integrating spectral unmixing with appearance-aware rendering and interactive visual tools (SimTex) allows conservators to toggle between hypothesized original states and forecasted fading scenarios, grounded in accelerated aging data and documentary photographs. The method balances chemical plausibility with perceptual realism, acknowledging uncertainties from photographic variability and incomplete dye mock-up coverage.

For early colour photographs and films, we advanced multispectral ‘silver/dye decoupling’ to restore autochromes (including severely faded blue dyes) and explored neural restoration of “greening” defects trained on synthetic data; for Kodacolor, we improved digital decoding through targeted finetuning of deep models for lenticule boundary detection, recovering historically plausible colours from lenticular scans.

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